

Research and Applications

Exploring student attitudes in astrobiology laboratory sessions within an astronomical observatory: A questionnaire-based study

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Astrobiology is a crosscutting science that bridges multiple disciplines, yet it remains largely absent from science curricula in Italian high schools, as well as in many other countries. The Astronomical Observatory of the Autonomous Region of the Aosta Valley (OAVdA) has developed a laboratory activity aimed at engaging students with astrobiology, leveraging its connection to exoplanet research. This activity serves as a tool to spark curiosity about the search for life beyond Earth and to foster a deeper appreciation of astronomy as an evolving field of scientific exploration. To assess its impact, students participated in a three-stage questionnaire process: before, immediately after, and a few weeks following the activity. The initial questionnaire gauged prior knowledge and interest in astrobiology, while the second captured shifts in perception and engagement. The third, designed to measure long-term retention, was ultimately excluded from statistical analysis due to inconsistencies in responses. With more than three hundred responses collected for each of the first two phases, the study revealed notable changes in students' self-awareness and perspectives on astrobiology's role in scientific research. Beyond its educational implications, this activity highlights the potential of hands-on, inquiry-based experiences in astronomy communication. While astrobiology proved to be an engaging topic, the results suggest that complementary approaches are needed to effectively address persistent misconceptions about astronomical research.

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1. Introduction

Laboratory and practical activities play a crucial role in engaging audiences with astronomy, and can be used to improve students' learning experience and problem-solving skills (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2003; Abrahams & Reiss, 2012; Hanson & Acquah, 2014; Rakhmonkulov & Usarov, 2019). Hands-on experiences have long been recognised as effective tools for deepening understanding, not only

in formal educational settings but also in science outreach and communication ([Hofstein & Lunetta, 2003](#); [Abrahams & Reiss, 2012](#); [Hanson & Acquah, 2014](#); [Rakhmonkulov & Usarov, 2019](#)).

Practical and collaborative activities are especially valuable for enhancing learning, as students find them both enjoyable and effective ([McKinney & Denton, 2006](#)), this also aids students' understanding the connection between theory and real-world applications ([Leopold & Smith, 2019](#)). [Neumann and Welzel \(2007\)](#) state that laboratory learning is the most important bridge between theory and practice, finding that practical work helped their audience in long-term memorisation. Practical activities in groups seem to also improve personal efficacy and success, allowing the development of social skills in a controlled environment ([Ding & Harskamp, 2010](#); [Leopold & Smith, 2019](#)). Despite these benefits, simply allowing participants to conduct experiments is insufficient; activities must be designed with clear learning objectives in mind, emphasising the connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications. If the laboratory structure is not appropriate, students risk failing to grasp the purpose of their activities ([Reid & Shah, 2007](#)), leading to ineffective learning. This often occurs when the educator does not clarify the activity's goals, fails to facilitate follow-up discussions, or employs 'cookbook' experiments without proper context. Moreover, people attending the activity will not inherently develop collaborative skills, interest in the subject, or effective knowledge just by being placed in smaller groups within a laboratory setting. Assuming that these outcomes will emerge without a proper design reflects what [Chang et al. \(2005\)](#) describe as magical thinking—the mistaken belief that certain educational goals will materialise spontaneously, without active facilitation.

The Astronomical Observatory of the Autonomous Region of the Aosta Valley (OAVdA) in Italy, situated at 1675 m above sea level, is a research institution that aims to incorporate science research and communication and to enrich the experiences of students, teachers, and tourists during their visits. Focusing on formal education, the institution offers an extensive range of programmes, from nighttime guided tours with observation of the sky through the telescopes to laboratory activities tailored for various age groups, from primary school to college-level participants, covering different astronomy-related topics.

Among the various activities offered by the OAVdA, a laboratory on astrobiology is available for high school students. This programme stems from OAVdA's multi-year research on exoplanet photometric transits around M stars and its contributions to exoplanet discovery ([Damasso et al., 2010](#); [Desidera et al., 2014](#)). This laboratory activity includes a lecture, discussion, and practical work. It lasts two hours and requires no prior astrobiology knowledge, as all necessary information is provided in the introductory lecture. The laboratory aims to introduce or deepen understanding of the subject, foster debate, build confidence in using professional equipment, and highlight the value of astrobiological and astronomical research ([Hallsworth et al., 2021](#)). Encouraged by the spontaneous feedback from our audience, we decided to investigate the effects of the activity, highlighting its strengths and areas for improvement. Specifically we

aimed to investigate the effects in students' attitude towards astrobiology (and scientific methodology in general).

2. Activity description

2.1 Lecture The activity was integrated into the OAVdA's programmes in 2021. Our target audience is high school students aged approximately 14 to 19, regardless of the specific school type. In Italy, students choose their secondary education path at age 13, selecting from options such as science, languages, humanities, and technology.

The activity aims to enhance engagement and interest in science and astronomy while fostering critical thinking and self-awareness. The introductory lecture, lasting 30 to 45 minutes and supported by a multimedia presentation, is crucial for clarifying the goals of the practical activity ([Reid & Shah, 2007](#)). It provides a framework for understanding the laboratory's purpose and offers foundational knowledge about astrobiology.

During the lecture, the speaker engages students through questions and storytelling, making the session more interactive and captivating ([Burns et al., 2003](#); [Bucchi & Trench, 2014](#)) and trying to earn their trust. This is done by highlighting intriguing stories—such as that of the extremophile *Bathynomus giganteus*, Milne-Edwards, 1879, whose unusual appearance may have inspired the design of the Predator movie monster—and by prompting students with open-ended questions, like how they would search for exoplanets. As [Bray et al. \(2012\)](#) note, understanding the audience is vital for effective science communication and establishing a reciprocal connection ([van der Sanden & Meijman, 2008](#)). In this context, astrobiology as a field often leverages curiosity to foster engagement. The speaker adopts this same approach to help students overcome initial bashfulness and feel comfortable asking questions, which can be addressed immediately or during the practical activity, enriching the learning experience ([Quinlan, 2015](#)).

The lecture begins by introducing the definition of astrobiology, followed by an overview of the Solar System and the Milky Way. Students are then invited to reason about exoplanets and the definition of habitable zone ([Kasting et al., 1993](#); [Underwood et al., 2003](#); [Schwieterman et al., 2019](#)). The discussion continues by challenging students to consider whether life might exist outside the habitable zone, through an astrobiological perspective focused on our own Solar System ([Nealson, 1997](#); [Lipps et al., 2004](#); [Shapiro & Schulze-Makuch, 2009](#); [Norman, 2011](#); [Petrescu et al., 2018](#)). At this point, the lecture highlights that some planets or moons in the Solar System exhibit environmental conditions similar to extreme habitats on Earth. This opens the discussion to extremophiles, with a focus on diatoms and tardigrades. Diatoms are presented as widespread eukaryotes capable of surviving in a broad range of conditions, and are also used to illustrate that life can appear unexpectedly “non-living” due to their rigid and geometric silicate shell ([Kocielek, 2007](#)). Tardigrades are introduced as iconic extremophiles,

renowned for their cryptobiosis state that enables them to survive in extreme environments, including outer space ([Jönsson & Bertolani, 2001](#); [Guidetti et al., 2011](#); [Tsujiimoto et al., 2016](#)). The key message students are encouraged to take away is that life may not always resemble what we typically imagine.

2.2 Laboratory After the lecture, the speaker guides the class to the adjacent laboratory, ready for the activity. The session simulates real scientific teamwork, aiming to help students grasp the challenges of astrobiological research while using professional tools and methods to deepen their understanding of how science is practiced. It features three tables, set up to allow up to eight students to work together. On each table students find:

- A box with clean microscope slides, coverslips and a pipette
- A biological microscope with three objective lenses (4x, 10x, 40x)
- A touch screen laptop
- A microscope digital camera, located on one of the oculars of the microscope and connected to the laptop via USB
- Cables for charging both the laptop and the microscope
- A pen or pencil
- A white sheet
- A laboratory check-list

The students are divided into three groups performing the same tasks. The activity begins with a review of microscope operation and the initiation of the ToupView software, which is used to control the camera. At this point, the speaker adopts a tutor-like role, guiding the groups toward greater independence.

Initially, students familiarise themselves with the microscope and software using generic slides, such as animal tissue samples. Each group member is encouraged to observe through both the microscope and computer. Once confident, they prepare a slide with a sample, from the paludarium of the laboratory, that may contain diatoms; this step simulates sample collection and preparation in scientific research.

In the next step, each group receives a slide with fixed diatoms, the purpose is to find an interesting one, focus it at maximum magnification and print the image. If successful, they can measure and classify the diatom via *Diatoms of North America*. The final step involves preparing a slide that may contain tardigrades. Students receive a petri dish with hydrated lichen from the *Xanthoria* genus ([Rebecchi et al., 2006](#); [Satkauskiene, 2012](#)), which grows near the OAVdA ([Piervittori & Isocrano, 1999](#); [Osservatorio della Biodiversità della Regione Autonoma Valle d'Aosta - Ricerca Licheni, 2024](#)) and often hosts dehydrated tardigrades.

The lichen has been pre-hydrated by the speaker to ensure students can collect samples without tardigrades remaining in cryptobiosis. Inside the box, students find a concave slide and must determine the correct orientation before collecting a drop of water from the lichen to prepare their slide for observation. If nobody finds a tardigrade, the tutor can prepare another sample or show an image of previously collected tardigrades. At the end of the activity, the guide wraps up the session by highlighting the students' teamwork, their use of professional tools, and the connections to the astrobiology concepts discussed during the lecture.

3. Methods

3.1 Study design Three similar questionnaires, with questions and answers collected in Italian, were built, each one consisting of a first part with demographic data, and a second part with close and open-ended questions. The questionnaires are anonymous according to [European Commission DG Research & Innovation \(2021\)](#) and the data were collected and processed in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulations.

The first questionnaire was administered before any activities at the OAVdA, the second at the end of the laboratory session, and the third online about three weeks later. The first two questionnaires were printed and distributed directly to students.

The questionnaires included 15 multiple-choice questions on an asymmetric five-point Likert scale ([Joshi et al., 2015](#)) to capture student opinions, along with two open-ended questions only on the second and third questionnaires, to explore additional outcomes ([Peterson, 2000](#)). The use of Likert scale questions allows for easier analysis ([Peterson, 2000](#)), includes a neutral response option ([Joshi et al., 2015](#)), and produces clear results. Each question targeted a single concept ([Nemoto & Beglar, 2014](#)). The five-point scale was chosen to enable nuanced student responses. Further details are available in the supplementary material.

In this preliminary study, we were interested in gaining insight into three main questions, inspired by the big ideas expressed by the IAU ([Big Ideas in Astronomy, n.d.](#)):

- I. Is the laboratory activity able to effectively convey the concepts and the methodologies of astrobiology?
- II. Is the activity able to enhance awareness about astrobiology concrete applications and contributions?
- III. Does the activity effectively engage the students, encouraging their curiosity and participation in scientific activities?

From all questionnaire entries we selected 11 key questions to compare the responses in the first and second questionnaires. We focused on the evolution of responses to questions directly investigating the main concepts introduced during the activity. Questions not included in this analysis, while potentially providing useful information, were not directly pertinent to

the primary objectives of this evaluation. Furthermore, the decision to analyse only identical questions in the pre- and post-lab questionnaires was made to strengthen the internal validity of the study, ensuring that observed changes in responses could be reasonably attributed to the lab intervention rather than to differences in question wording. The third questionnaire has been excluded due to unreliability of responses and scarcity of data. We divided the questions into two main macro-categories, namely:

1. **Perspectives**, assessing variation of knowledge and attitude towards astrobiology. This category concerns research questions I and II.
2. **Self-awareness**, assessing the perceived ability to perform in science (research question III).

Moreover, for a more effective visualisation of the results, we operated a sub-classification of the first category **Perspectives** into two themes: “Notions”, and “Usefulness”.

The “Notion” category included the following questions:

Notions-q1. Is astrobiology a pseudoscience?

Notions-q2. Are we currently able to reach other planets within our Solar System?

Notions-q3. Are we currently able to reach other planets outside our Solar System?

The “Usefulness” category included the following questions:

Usefulness-q1. Can the search for other planets capable of harboring life help us understand our own?

Usefulness-q2. I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms has direct utility, that is, that research results can be translated into objects, tools and knowledge that can be applied in our daily lives.

Usefulness-q3. I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms has indirect utility, i.e., that research results can contribute to technological advancement, even if not immediately applicable.

Usefulness-q4. INV (inverted scale). I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms is futile.

Finally, the “Self-awareness” category included the following questions:

Self-awareness-q1. I think I am capable of using scientific laboratory materials.

Self-awareness-q2. I think I could contribute to scientific research activities, with the knowledge I have now.

Self-awareness-q3. I am able to work within a scientific staff.

Self-awareness-q4. I think I am able to work together with other people.

We also used the open questions from the second questionnaire to complement the dataset with the students’ positive and negative opinions naturally emerging.

3.2 Participants The participants were previously informed about the possibility of refusing to answer all or part of the questionnaires. The questionnaires were anonymous according to [European Commission DG Research & Innovation \(2021\)](#) and the data were collected and processed in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulations. The OAVdA activities in this study were offered to high school students aged 14 to 21 from various types of Italian secondary schools. The 385 participants, aged 14 to 21, attended Italian licei (a kind of Italian secondary school that provides a strong academic foundation, lasting five years and preparing students for university studies) with curricula in science, languages, or humanities. No participants were excluded a priori.

3.3 Data Analysis Our analysis is divided into two parts: first, exploratory and statistical analyses evaluate attitudes toward notions, usefulness and self-awareness, and second, basic text analysis identifies key positive and negative participant feedback.

Responses were transcribed into electronic datasheets and pre-processed through data cleaning and category aggregation. The two questionnaires were merged to retain temporal information, with responses from the first collected before the activities and from the second afterward.

Two datasets were created: one for statistical analysis, containing demographic data (gender, class, field of study) and 11 key questions, and another with demographic data and two open-ended questions. All missing values were removed. This separation preserved maximum information; for instance, if a student completed all 11 questions but skipped an open-ended question, their data was still included in the statistical analysis, and vice versa.

After data cleaning, we aggregated certain demographic levels to ensure sufficient data points for meaningful analysis:

- Classes 1 and 2 were combined into “1st class cycle,” and classes 3 to 5 as “2nd class cycle,” in line with the Italian high school system, to capture potential differences in student responses.
- Curriculum categories (scientific, classical, linguistic) were converted to a binary format: “scientific” or “other.” This grouping emphasised differences between scientific and non-scientific programmes while creating more balanced data groups.

We condensed the Likert scale responses from five levels to three: values 1 and 2 were grouped as “NO,” values 4 and 5 as “YES,” and value 3 as “MAYBE.” This simplification enhances statistical analysis and interpretability ([Jacoby & Matell, 1971](#); [Tractenberg et al., 2007](#)). For better visualisation and interpretation, responses to the usefulness question (q4) were inverted, mapping values 4 and 5 to “NO” and values 1 and 2 to “YES.”

3.3.1 Statistical analysis The statistical analysis focused on the comparison between the responses given before the activities with respect to the ones given after. We also assess the

potential influence of demographic factors (gender, class and field of study) on the responses values. We stated the three research questions mentioned above into the following null/alternative hypotheses and we conducted a Chi-square test ([Pearson, 1900](#)) for each question:

H0: Activities have no effect on the the response, i.e. response in Questionnaire2 (after the activities) did not change with respect Questionnaire1 (before the activities)

H1: The experience at the observatory produced an evolution of the response, i.e. Questionnaire1 and Questionnaire2 responses are different.

The statistical analysis has been done with *scipy* ([Virtanen et al., 2020](#)) and *statsmodel* ([Seabold & Perktold, 2010](#)).

3.3.2 Text analysis In the second questionnaire, students could provide positive or negative feedback about the experience. Each response was treated as a document, and all responses formed the corpus for text analysis. We preprocessed each document using standard text processing techniques, including spell-checking, tokenisation, stemming, lemmatisation, POS (part-of-speech) tagging (the process of assigning a grammatical category tag to each word in the text), and stop-word removal ([Yogish et al., 2019](#)). In addition to common stop words, we removed words from the question itself (e.g., “what,” “thing,” “impressed”) and generic terms like “activity” and “fact.”

Text processing relied on two Python packages: *NLTK* ([Bird et al., 2009](#)) and *SpaCy* ([Honnibal & Montani, 2017](#)), with manual checks of each step. For negative responses, we addressed answers where students included positive points followed by a “but” by isolating and analysing only sentences with negative content. We also recorded responses that were empty or stated no negative aspects.

Our text analysis used the “bag of words” approach ([Zhang et al., 2010](#)), creating a dictionary of all terms and examining term frequencies within and across documents. We highlighted the most frequent nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs to identify key positive and negative aspects. Next, we applied a Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model ([Blei et al., 2003](#)) to uncover main topics in both the positive and negative response corpora. Each response was mapped into a vector space using TF-IDF transformation ([Baeza-Yates & Ribeiro-Neto, 2011](#)), and we tested several LDA models with varying topic numbers, evaluating coherence, log-likelihood, and perplexity scores ([Tijare & Jhansi Rani, 2020](#)) to select the best model.

4. Results

4.1 Sample characterisation The responses from the third questionnaire were excluded from the analysis due to their unreliability (only about a third of the questionnaires were collected and these included a significant number of unanswered questions). The low response rate may be attributed to our inability to directly administer the follow-up questionnaire to the

students, instead, a link was sent to the teachers, who then forwarded it to the students. Moreover, no follow-up activities were organised by the teachers after the visit to the OAVdA facility, so the students were probably involved in other activities leading to a decreased interest in our questionnaires. However these remain only speculations, as we didn't have the opportunity to meet the students again after the visit. We attempted to analyse the limited data obtained from the third questionnaire, but no statistically relevant information could be extracted. We collected 381 responses in the first questionnaire and 383 in the second. After cleaning, our dataset for statistical analysis includes 731 responses (356 valid responses from the first questionnaire and 369 from the second) to 11 selected questions on a 5-level Likert scale, along with demographic data. The text analysis dataset includes these same demographic fields plus 363 responses highlighting positive aspects and 250 responses noting negative aspects, provided as free text by participants. Descriptive statistics are shown in [Table 1](#).

Questionnaire	Gender	Count	Class Cycle		Field of Study (bool)	
			First	Second	Scientific	Other
1	Male	173	81	92	134	39
	Female	178	71	107	161	17
	Other	5	1	4	5	0
2	Male	179	81	98	139	40
	Female	185	77	108	166	19
	Other	5	2	3	5	0

Table 1 Sample characterization divided by gender, class cycle and field of study. In both questionnaires there is a slight difference between the number of male and female participants, with only a few indicating "Other" as their gender. There is also a higher number of participants from the second cycle of study (corresponding to the third to fifth years of high school) and a marked prevalence of students from the scientific liceo.

In the sample, 49.6% of participants identified as male, 49.0% as female, and 1.4% as other. Students from the 1st high school cycle comprised 42.9%, while 57.1% were from the 2nd cycle. Although all students attended a liceo, most were from science-focused high schools (84.4%), with the remaining 15.6% from linguistic and humanities programmes.

4.2 Evolution of the answers before and after the experience We examined the impact of OAVdA activities on the three selected categories. For each related question, we compared the percentages of "NO," "MAYBE," and "YES" responses from before the experience (first questionnaire) to those after (second questionnaire). Results are displayed in the Likert plots in [Figures 1, 2, and 3](#). Graphs using the full 5-level Likert scale, along with group-specific results (e.g., by gender, field of study, or school cycle), are available in the supplementary materials.

Figure 1 Variation in the “Notions” category. Percentages below 10% are not displayed in the plots. For q1, the correct answer was “NO”; for q2, it was “YES”; and for q3, it was “NO.” A significant decrease in uncertainty (“MAYBE” responses) is observed for q1, while it remains relatively stable for q2 and q3. We also observe a significant increase in the correct answer to q1, alongside a slight decrease in the incorrect answers to q2 and q3.

Figure 2 Variation in the “Usefulness” category. Percentages below 10% are not displayed in the plots. The questions assess students’ perception of the utility of astrobiological research: q1 evaluates whether studying planets capable of harboring life can help us understand our own; q2 and q3 explore the belief in the direct and indirect utility of such research, respectively; q4 (already inverted) examines whether students consider this research futile. The desired answer for all questions is ‘YES’, with a significant increase observed for q1, while q2, q3, and q4 show moderate improvements or, in the case of q4, a slight decline.

Figure 3 Variation in the “Usefulness” category. Percentages below 10% are not displayed in the plots. All questions show an increase in the desired response (“YES”), with a reduction in uncertainty for all questions except q3 and q4. The fourth question displays less variation compared to the others, with students showing more consistency in their answers.

Question label	Question	p-value	Mann-Whitney statistics
notions-q1	Is Astrobiology a pseudoscience?	<1e-4	77954
notions-q2	Are we currently able to reach other planets within our Solar System?	0.085	62168
notions-q3	Are we currently able to reach other planets outside our Solar System?	0.94	66598
usefulness-q1	Can the search for other planets capable of harboring life help us understand our own?	<1e-8	51508
usefulness-q2	I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms has direct utility, that is, that research results can be translated into objects, tools and knowledge that can be applied in our daily lives.	0.008	59436
usefulness-q3	I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms has indirect utility, i.e., that research results can contribute to technological advancement, even if not immediately applicable.	0.002	58573
usefulness-q4-INV	I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms is futile.	0.25	69608
self-awareness-q1	I think I am capable of using scientific laboratory materials.	<1e-20	38354
self-awareness-q2	I think I could contribute to scientific research activities, with the knowledge I have now.	<1e-18	41842
self-awareness-q3	I believe I am able to work within a scientific staff.	<1e-18	41703
self-awareness-q4	I think I am able to work together with other people.	0.002	58697

Table 2 Results of the application of the Mann-Whitney test on the two questionnaires (before and after the activity). The third column indicates the p-value while the fourth column reports the test statistics.

Overall, we found that Self-awareness showed the greatest increase in positive responses after the experience, rising by about 20 percentage points on average. This suggests that OAVdA activities had a strong positive impact on students' confidence in teamwork and research, especially considering that most of the students didn't really know anything about astrobiology. Perceptions of astrobiology's usefulness saw a little rise in positive responses of about 6 percentage points on average – except for question Usefulness-q4-INV.

For knowledge-based questions, we observed a notable increase (around 20 percentage points) in students correctly identifying that astrobiology is not pseudoscience, though responses on space reachability showed a slight decline in accuracy. A Chi-square test confirmed that many of these changes were statistically significant at a confidence level of $\alpha=0.05$ (see [Table 2](#)).

Each question's qualitative and quantitative results are discussed in detail below.

Notions In question q1, before the experience, the desired answer was given by 32.7% of the participants, 21.4% had a wrong notion about astrobiology as pseudoscience, the remaining were uncertain. In the second questionnaire the percentage of uncertain students decreased from 45.9% to 19.6%, so the students acquired more confidence in responding with a more oriented correct answer (the correct answers increased up to 53.1%). The percentages of correct answers to question q2 and q3 was high in the first questionnaire (78.6% and 79.9%) but both show a slight decrease after the activities in OAVdA. Among notions questions only q1 resulted in variations statistically significant before and after the experience.

Usefulness All questions except q4 showed a decrease in "NO" and "MAYBE" answers in favor of "YES." The variation was most evident in q1, where the percentage increased from 81.6% to 89.0%. For the other questions, the shift was from 70.4% to 75.8% and from 70.7% to 74.5%, respectively. In q4, responses remained almost unchanged, with a slight increase in incorrect answers. This suggests a decline in students' perception of the usefulness of astrobiological research, which contradicts the trends observed in q1, q2, and q3. However, the results of the Chi-square test and the Mann-Whitney test indicate a statistically significant variation only for q1, q2, and q3. It is worth noting that, even though the shift between "YES" and "NO" answers was not particularly pronounced, the change from "PROBABLY YES" to "CERTAINLY YES" was more evident. For instance, in q3, this shift went from 27% to 47.6%, suggesting a stronger conviction after the laboratory experience.

Self-awareness The comparison of the answers related to self-awareness before and after the experience at OAVdA highlighted two very different scenarios: in the first questionnaire only 38.1% of the students believed that they can use laboratory material, 71.2% in the second questionnaire. This was the most evident variation in responses, followed by q3, where the percentage of students that are confident in working in a scientific team changed from 21.1% to 45.4%. In question q2 we highlight the fact that

the participants who did not feel they can contribute to a research were 72.1% while after they almost halved (44.5%). We also note that in q2 there is an evident increase for the uncertainty answer, this may indicate some cognitive conflict or a tendency towards a better confidence, but investigating that requires a dedicated study. The last question, q4, even if similar to q3, showed a less positive variation (a difference of 3% between the two questionnaires). This question is related to team-working abilities, while q3 is more specific about scientific staff. The values of Chi-squared test verify, with a level of confidence of 0.05, that q1, q2 and q3 answers before and after the experience are statistically different, with p-value lower than 10⁻³.

4.3 Text analysis of participants feedback We collected a total of 363 valid responses regarding the positive aspects and 73 regarding the negative aspects. Notably, 81% (312 responses) of the negative feedback was either empty or indicated no negative aspects, while 3% (13 responses) provided mixed feedback. Two nonsensical responses were excluded from the analysis. After processing the text, nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs were extracted for further analysis.

Positive vs. Negative Feedback

- Positive Feedback: The top concepts mentioned included practical activities such as “water bears,” “laboratory”, and “microscope.”
- Negative Feedback: Students expressed concerns about limited time, prior misconceptions, gaps in knowledge, and unfavourable weather conditions which prevented nighttime observations with the eyepieces of the telescopes (the latter being, of course, beyond our control).
- Positive feedback averaged 5.2 selected terms per response, while negative feedback averaged 3.4 terms.

[Figures 4](#) and [5](#) illustrate the top terms for both positive and negative feedback were also included in the analysis.

The second phase of the analysis involved applying LDA to identify the main topics arising from both positive and negative feedback. Various topic counts (from 2 to 7) were tested, and the optimal results were found with n_topic=3 for positive feedback and n_topic=1 for negative feedback.

Positive Feedback: Three distinct topics emerged:

- Discovery Actions: Terms such as “discover,” “find,” “know,” and “study.”
- Practical Activities: Keywords included “planetarium,” “water bears”, “microscope,” and “laboratory,” often paired with adjectives like “interesting.”
- Theoretical Knowledge: Focused on terms like “Universe” and “Solar System,” along with

Figure 4 Text Analysis - Word Count. Students' answers to the open-ended question on positive feedback indicate that the most impactful element was the tardigrade, mentioned over 70 times, followed by the laboratory activity. Italian words are available upon request to the corresponding author.

Figure 5 Text Analysis - Word Count. Students' answers to the open-ended question on negative feedback shows a lower response rate and a tendency to refer to general problems, not always related with the activity or the lecture. Italian words are available upon request to the corresponding author.

concepts related to explanation.

Negative Feedback: Topic modeling identified a single topic encompassing some concerns:

- Weather: Concerns regarding cloudy, rainy, or cold conditions affecting visibility during observations. These comments were taken into account, however they referred to the visual observations of the night sky following the activity, not to the laboratory per se.
- Duration: Feedback indicated that the activities felt too short relative to what was scheduled.
- Activity Engagement: Some activities were perceived as boring, trivial, or lacking impact.

5. Discussion

The study assessed the impact of a two-hour practical activity at the OAVdA on students' attitudes toward astrobiology and science. We decided to investigate three research questions: whether the activity could convey the concepts and the methodologies of astrobiology, enhance awareness about astrobiology, and effectively engage the students by encouraging their curiosity and participation in scientific activities. Given the short duration, changing misconceptions was challenging, consistent with [Abrahams & Millar \(2008\)](#), who highlighted the need of a proper amount of time to help students connect the results of the practical task with the ideas associated with the phenomena they have produced.

Despite starting with no prior knowledge, students quickly learned to use research tools and conduct experiments. While enthusiasm was evident, the activity had limited success in correcting misconceptions. The most significant post-activity change was about Usefulness-q1, *Can the search for other planets capable of harboring life help us understand our own?, warranting further investigation.*

Still, students provided highly positive feedback, suggesting the activity effectively sparked interest and introduced new concepts, potentially encouraging future interest in science ([Fredricks, 2011](#)). A key outcome was the boost in students' confidence with lab equipment: initially viewing research as something for experts, they came to see it as a learning process accessible to all. This aligns with the Italian Ministry of Education's recommendation to incorporate practical activities across all educational levels to enhance learning ([MIM, 2023](#)).

The activity significantly reduced uncertainty about whether astrobiology is a pseudoscience, with fewer neutral responses and more "NO" or "PROBABLY NOT". Although incorrect answers slightly increased, the change was not statistically significant. Still, about 25% of participants believed astrobiology to be a pseudoscience, warranting further investigation. This may stem from unfamiliarity with the term "pseudoscience", which we defined in a footnote: 'A theory, doctrine, or current of thought claiming scientific status without a scientific foundation' ([Pseudoscienza - Treccani, 2023](#)). Despite the activity, incorrect responses did not decrease but slightly increased. Possible explanations include:

1. Participants didn't know the meaning of the word and didn't read the definition;
2. Participants read the meaning of the word, but didn't understand it;
3. Participants knew or read the definition, but the activity led them to perceive astrobiology as not entirely scientific.
4. Participants misunderstood the nature of science itself, leading to misclassification.

Of all the possibilities, the second seems unlikely given the results of the PISA-OCSE analysis (2023), which showed that Italian students outperform students from other OCSE countries in reading (Ricci et al., 2022).

Notions-q2, *Are we currently able to reach other planets within our Solar System?*, was intentionally left open to allow interpretations involving human travel, probes, or both. Despite efforts to clarify this during the conference, some students focused only on human missions, disregarding the role of probes and rovers. Interestingly, incorrect responses increased after the activity, suggesting a shift in how students interpreted the term "reach", though exploring this further is beyond the study's scope. A similar pattern appeared with Notions-q3, *Are we currently able to reach other planets outside our Solar System?*, where more students believed we could reach exoplanets. These outcomes may reflect cognitive conflict, as described by Kingsley et al. (2019), with students revising prior knowledge.

The Usefulness category of questions explored students' perceptions of astrobiology's utility. As stated above, responses showed only slight changes after the activity, except for Usefulness-q1, *Can the search for other planets capable of harboring life help us understand our own?*. The introductory lecture emphasised extreme environments, both on Earth and in space, that might support life, highlighting the relevance of studying the possibility of extraterrestrial life to better understand life on Earth.

Astrobiology integrates multiple disciplines: astronomy, biology, chemistry, geology, physics, and even philosophy. This positions Earth as both a model and a subject of study (Cottin et al., 2015), a concept students appeared to grasp before the lab, as only one question showed a notable improvement in accuracy. A slight decrease was observed in Usefulness-q4-INV, *I believe that the search for possible extraterrestrial life forms is futile*, but it was not significant and may be attributed to confusion or response bias (Swain et al., 2008; Sonderen et al., 2013).

The Self-awareness category focused on students' approach to science, particularly regarding scientific research and the use of lab materials. This stemmed from past observations where students, surprised by their own abilities, expressed sentiments like "I didn't think I could do this!", raising questions about their perception of science as something accessible beyond textbooks. This category showed the greatest change, with three out of four questions reflecting increased positive responses about one's own capability to carry out an experiment in a science team. Higher self-esteem is linked to improved academic performance (Corbière et al., 2006; Yazici et al., 2011), motivation, and persistence in learning (Schunk, 1985), though

this relationship is shaped by multiple factors ([Troncone et al., 2014](#); [Valenti & Faraci, 2021](#)). Practical activities, such as those proposed in OAVdA, play a key role in boosting students' self-confidence ([Bandura, 1977; 1982](#)).

This study highlights a clear increase in students' confidence in their scientific abilities, though self-assessed teamwork skills remained unchanged. It would be valuable to further explore students' beliefs about what is required to engage in science beyond technical knowledge. Notably, nearly one-third initially felt unable to use lab materials: this represents an issue, as low self-esteem can inflate perceived task difficulty, while self-confidence fosters resilience even under pressure ([van Dinther et al., 2011](#)).

To better capture students' perspectives, two open-ended questions were included, which provided insights not addressed in the closed items and offered guidance for improving future educational activities ([Gottipati et al., 2017](#)). Text analysis revealed a strong imbalance between positive and negative comments, suggesting that students perceived the activity favorably and were inclined to emphasise its constructive aspects.

Notably, gender, curriculum, and school cycle had no apparent influence on any responses.

6. Conclusions

Our research aimed to assess the effectiveness of an astrobiology laboratory activity proposed by OAVdA for students visiting the facility from Italian high schools. We measured changes in participants' attitudes through pre- and post-activity questionnaires. The results supported previous findings regarding the benefits of practical activities in science communication and education. While hands-on experiences enhance learning, contextualising these activities within the school curriculum is crucial for building new knowledge. Our findings highlight the effectiveness of such activities in improving students' confidence and developing essential skills for future scientific pursuits. Statistical analysis revealed significant shifts in participants' confidence across various self-awareness dimensions, indicating that laboratory activities positively influence students' confidence in collaborative scientific work. However, changes in other areas - such as understanding astrobiology, recognising its practical applications, and perceiving its usefulness - were less pronounced. Our study suggests that while laboratory activities can effectively enhance students' confidence in scientific teamwork, further exploration or alternative approaches may be necessary to shift perceptions of astrobiology and its relevance.

This type of analysis can inform the development of targeted interventions to enhance students' attitudes toward scientific fields like astrobiology. Investigating the factors that shape students' perceptions of astrobiology and its usefulness could prove beneficial. This might include exploring different communication strategies or integrating complementary educational interventions to effectively convey the significance of astrobiology to students.

Given the interdisciplinary nature of astrobiology, future studies should consider collaborative efforts among educators, scientists, communicators and curriculum developers to create comprehensive educational experiences that integrate astrobiological concepts across diverse disciplines. It remains to be seen whether these results would hold in a different setting. By addressing these avenues, we can advance science communication and cultivate a generation of scientifically literate individuals equipped with the skills, knowledge, and confidence to tackle the challenges of tomorrow's world.

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